

THE IMPORTANCE OF TEACHING COMPOSITION AND ITS ROLE IN STUDENTS' CREATIVE ACTIVITY**Shomurodov Oybek**

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Abstract. The composition course allows the student to think figuratively and develop creative imagination, to develop the skills of seeing beauty and news in life, to summarize events and events, and to describe inner feelings in artistic images.

Keywords: composition, student, creative, imagination

The main goal of teaching composition to students is to train an artist-pedagogue who has acquired high skill and deep visual culture, humanitarian and realism methods based on national spirituality and moral traditions. However, due to the limited time allotted for the composition course according to the curriculum, the student may not be able to gain enough knowledge during this time.

That is why it is necessary to sufficiently enrich students' theoretical knowledge of composition during composition training and strengthen this knowledge in practical, independent training.

Students' knowledge of composition can be enriched not only in composition classes, but also in pencil drawing, painting, design, and painting classes. Teaching composition is carried out from the first course by increasing the complexity of each task in a certain sequence. This is done during the performance of educational tasks in composition, as well as in the course of working on educational tasks in painting and pencil drawing. In these classes, methods such as the correct use of the surface of the drawing plane, the development of qualities such as the overall perception of the composition, the center of the composition, and the diagonal solution are also explained in these classes.

The rules of indivisibility of the composition are symmetry, knowledge of asymmetry will help to perform more complex compositions in the future.

Our reality is the main source of representation and learning in the composition works that students create. A necessary condition for working on the composition is the collection of life observations, which is carried out by the student regularly as a result of recording in etudes and plates, drawing from nature, observation, memory and imagination. These tasks are performed during independent classes of pencil drawing and painting.

For example, independent exercises given to a student from a pencil drawing or painting can be given in the following sequence.

1. Make a composition based on a still life and place it correctly in the composition.
2. Interior composition. (placing items and linking subject content through these items).
3. Individual work for a sketch on a given (or student's own) topic.
(interviews, trips to museums or industrial enterprises to collect material for the composition, reading literature, taking pictures, etc.).
4. Through observation, composition work (nature scene, thematic picture).
5. Exercises to learn the compositional correct placement of a group of people. (interior, exterior and nature)

In the process of performing these tasks, the teacher should teach the student to think

about his life impressions, educate them in the spirit of being able to see and truthfully describe the typical events of life.

Among the specialization subjects in the curriculum of the "Fine Art and Engineering Graphics" undergraduate education, graphics and easel painting are included, and these subjects are taught in 7-8 semesters. These subjects can be called an organic continuation of the subject of composition taught in 5-6 semesters.

Composition training focuses on the role of composition in the art teacher's creative and pedagogical practice and methods of their practical application, while graphics and easel painting training teaches how to work on creating a finished work of art.

In the composition classes, the teacher teaches to work on the composition regularly and consistently. In this, the main attention is focused on choosing a topic, collecting material, working on a sketch, and learning to master the means of expressing the purpose, essence and topic, to find the necessary accuracy in a compositional solution.

Opening the whole difficult process of creating a composition before the student, the teacher focuses his attention on the most important solution of the goal, to distinguish the main one, to subordinate the secondary ones to it, to establish connections between the pieces of the composition, to subordinate them to the whole, color, color, light-shadows, silhouette, contrast, stasis and intensity, rhythm in colors and lights, all means must focus on achieving the integrity and balance of the composition.

This plan does not include tasks related to forms of graphic art (industrial, polygraphic, book). Because, as we mentioned above, graphic science is included in the curriculum, and by studying this science, the student can have all the theoretical information about graphic art and acquire the skills of creating compositions.

Before performing each practical task, the teacher explains to the students the basic laws and rules of the composition, which reveal the content and description of the topic, its essence. Before starting work on the sketch, the teacher offers the literature and resources necessary for students to study the topic in depth. The teacher also gives his advice during the work process. The student should pay attention to the fact that the methods of solving the subject are diverse, to use the system of contradictions, to correctly choose the form and volume, the point of view, perspective, scales, etc. Depending on the development of the students' activity, they are required to work on a consistent, neat work on the sketched materials, to work on the composition of pictures and sketches, sketches of various options.

After the sketch work is completed, the teacher shows the good and bad sides, achievements and shortcomings of the work done. In order to increase students' interest in composition classes, competitions for the best compositions on a given topic are held.

One task from the composition is performed on the basis of the materials collected during the summer internship.

Regardless of the direction of the qualification-graduation work that completes the study process, the composition should be a well-constructed work of art. This qualification-graduation work is a reflection of the various knowledge and experience acquired by the student in the process of studying at the university.

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